

Comparative Analyses and Statistical Measurement of PSNR and BER versus Different WLANs Transceiver Simulation Based on the Compression DCT and EICA Algorithms

*Mustafa Almahdi Algaet¹, Ali Milad², Munayr Amir³, Khalid Alajel⁴
Faculty of Information Technology / Elmergib university, libya^{1,2,3}

Department of Electrical and Computer System Engineering / Elmergib University, libya⁴

*Corresponding author: Mustafa Almahdi Algaet, Department of Network, Dean of Faculty of Information Technology, 40414 Alkhums Libya

Received: Nov 27, 2025

Accepted: Dec 22, 2025

Published: Dec 24, 2025

Abstract - a new approach called Enhanced Independent Component Analysis (EICA) for medical image compression has been developed to boost compression techniques; which transform the image data by block-based ICA. The proposed method uses Fast Independent Component Analysis (FastICA) algorithm followed by developed quantization architecture based zero quantized coefficients percentage (ZQCP) predation model using artificial neural network. For image reconstruction, decoding steps based the developed quantization architecture are examined. The EICA is particularly useful where the size of the transmitted data needs to be reduced to minimize the image transmission time. For data compression with suitable and effective performance, enhanced independent components analysis (EICA) is proposed as an algorithm for compression and decompression of medical data. A comparative analysis is performed based on existing data compression techniques: discrete cosine transform (DCT), Three main modules, namely, compression segment (CS), transceiver segment (TRS), and outcome segment (OTS) modules, are developed to realize a fully computerized simulation tool for medical data compression with suitable and effective performance. To compress medical data using algorithms, CS module involves four different approaches which are DCT and EICA. TRS module practice is processed by low-cost WLANs with low-bandwidth transmission. Finally, OTS is used for data decompression and visualization result. Performance evaluation during data compression comprises two procedures. First, performance results are associated to transmit and received similar data, which are exemplified by bit error rates, whereas the second performance considers the comparison between original and received images, CR used for calculation, peak signal-to-noise ratio, and mean square error. Finally, all three modules (CS, TRS, and OTS) are integrated to yield a computerized prototype named as Medical Data Simulation System (Medata-SIM). In terms of compression module, results show the benefits of applying EICA in medical data compression and transmission. In terms of system design, the developed system displays favourable outcomes in compressing and transmitting medical data. In conclusion, this paper developed a Medata-SIM computerized system that includes medical data compression and transceiver for visualization to aid medical practitioners in carrying out rapid diagnoses.

Keywords: DCT, EICA, Medata-SIM, Medical Data, Wi- Fi 802.11b

INTRODUCTION

In healthcare and hospital networks, medical data exchange-based wireless local area network (WLAN) transceivers remain challenging because of their growing data size, real-time contact with compressed images, and range of bandwidths requiring transmission support. Prior to transmission, medical data are compressed to minimize transmission bandwidth and save transmitting power. Researchers address many challenges in improving performance of

compression approaches. Such challenges include energy compaction, computational complexity, and high entropy value; drive low compression ratio (CR) and high computational complexity in real-time implementation[1].

Many recent clinical trials used telemedicine as their primary tool. This technology enables rapid diagnosis with visual and quantitative assessment, providing aid to health practitioners and professionals. Vastness of medical and healthcare sectors and their importance in ensuring quality of life of all citizens implies the significance of medical diagnosis with images. Thus, software, such as Medata-SIM, were further developed and used to assess medical data[2]. Medata-SIM software tool comprises three main segments, namely, CS, which is processed by DCT and EICA compression algorithms with acceptable compression performance; TRS, which is processed using Wi-Fi 802.11b with low bandwidth transmission; and outcome segment (OTS), which is used for decompression and results analysis.

MEDATA-SIM SYSTEM OVERVIEW

1. Block Diagram

Figure 1 shows the block diagram for the proposed Medata-SIM system; its individual parts can be processed separately as per requirement. Medical data can be classified into medical and X-ray images. CS is processed by compression techniques with acceptable CR and visual appearance performances, TRS is processed using Wi-Fi 802.11b with low bandwidth transmission, and OTS is used for decompression and results analysis[3].

Figure 1: Block diagram and overview of Medata-SIM proposed system

2. MEDICAL DATA

To diagnose diseases, medical data are generally used with different imaging modalities, such as CT, MRI, ultrasonography, and radiographs. These modalities provide flexibility in viewing anatomy and physiological conditions of cross sections. Nevertheless, medical data require large storage space. Prior to transmission and storage, medical data are compressed because of limited network bandwidth and storage capacity. Thus, techniques for compressing images are urgently needed to enable storage and phase reduction for storage and transmission[4].

Comprehension of medical data is necessary for medical purposes, where large volumes of digital images and video are used. Science of medical diagnosis data is commonly applied in medical source, physical scans, and studies of bodily structure, distant operations, and recovering accidents. Although priority is normally given to imaging of emergency cases, other urgent cases also require diagnostic imaging, such as MRI during operations, to show states of injuries during accidents. Figure 2 illustrates several samples of medical data[5].

Figure 2: Samples of medical data (a) X-Ray image, (b) fundus image and (C) cardiac ultrasound image

DESCRIPTION OF THE DESIGN FRAMEWORK

Three main modules, namely, CS, TRS, and OTS, are involved in the design framework for development of the proposed Medata-SIM system for medical data exchange and transmission. CS includes three different compression algorithms, namely, DCT, the proposed compression algorithm EICA, to compress medical data[6]. TRS module deals with implementation of WLAN transmission of compressed medical data using the IEEE 802.11b DBPSK modulation with different E_s/N_0 variations. Finally, collected medical data from TRS pass through OTS module for decompression and statistical measurement of compressed data. Figure 3 shows the main segments involved in Medata-SIM design framework. Detailed descriptions of the three main development segments are described in following sections and summarized in Table 1.

Figure 3: Screen shot and main interface of developed Medata-Sim prototype

Table 1 also summarizes items, names, and description functionality of the developed Medata-SIM prototype system.

TABLE 1: ITEMS, NAMES, AND DESCRIPTION FUNCTIONALITY OF THE DEVELOPED MEDATA-SIM

Names	Description
Source Menu	This item is used to open a desired data (Open File), Screening and display the selected medical data.
Compression Menu	This item composed of 2 different functions, setting and running process of the desired compression algorithm.
Transmission Menu	This item composed of 2 different process functions, setting and running process of the transmission approach.

Processing (Kamalrudin et al.)	This item for task of run and take functionality action of the above selected.
Receiver Menu	This item of screening and display the receiving results from the transmission stage.
Decompression Menu	This item for function of screening and display the Decompressing process of the desired compression algorithm.
Outcome Menu	This item for task of display the statistical measure of the received resulting data.

SYSTEM FUNCTIONALITY

This section provides details of the main segments involved in developing Medata- SIM system. Figure 4 shows the main segments of development process and establishment of each stage[7].

Figure 4: Block diagram of Medata-SIM proposed system functionality

COMPRESSION APPROACH SUMMARY

This section discusses the performance of evaluation of compression algorithms. Three types of medical data were compressed using different compression algorithms (i.e., DCT and EICA). The entire dataset has been employed to produce comparison includes 100 of each x-ray images, 100 of fundus images and 100 of cardiac ultrasound images[8]. Resulting compressed medical data were evaluated in terms of CR and PSNR. Figure 5 illustrate the mean PSNR and mean CR quantitative

measurements results, respectively by employing the proposed EICA with the different compression DCT algorithms.

1. In terms of PSNR performance, the results of the proposed EICA compression algorithm shown in Figure 5 using all medical data yielded a satisfactory quality image compared with other compression algorithm using DCT respectively. These measurement results are indicated in Table 2, where the PSNR quantitative measurement of DCT is shown to have mean PSNR of 34.3636 and EICA (33.788), respectively, which is found EICA to have the lowermost PSNR in entire medical datasets[9].

2. By contrast, in determining compression amount based on all medical data, mean CR scores obtained using the EICA algorithm were significantly higher than those obtained using DCT algorithms, respectively as shown in Figure 5.

3. In general, a significant improvement in mean CR was observed, with a mean score of 3.567 when using EICA compression algorithm compared with mean scores of 1.2986 using DCT algorithms, respectively.

Figure 5: Comparative analyses of mean (CR and PSNR) versus different compression algorithms

Table 2 provide detailed results obtained using DCT and EICA compression approaches to clarify comparative analysis based on obtained PSNR and CR scores for all medical data.

TABLE 2: COMPARATIVE STATISTICAL MEASUREMENT OBTAINED USING DCT AND EICA COMPRESSION ALGORITHMS

Image type \ Algorithms	Fundus Images		X-ray Images		CardiacUltrasound Images	
	Mean (CR)	Mean PSNR	Mean (CR)	Mean PSNR	Mean (CR)	Mean PSNR
DCT	1.2883	35.4903	1.1274	41.5039	1.4800	26.0966
EICA	3.1122	33.9298	3.6746	38.5743	3.9124	28.8599

In conclusion, CR and PSNR scores obtained using EICA for all medical data revealed that medical data can be compressed well with excellent compression ratio and satisfactory visual performances. The results show that best performance is achieved with EICA method both in terms of compression ratio and good PSNR. Figure 6 illustrates the visual interpretation of medical image

samples compressed using DCT based best blocking size (8 by 8) and selected DCT coefficient kept. Figure 7 illustrate the visual inspection of medical image samples compressed using DCT and EICA based selected parameters[10].

Figure 6: Visual inspection of medical image samples compressed using DCT based best blocking size (8 by 8) and selected DCT coefficient kept

Figure 7: Visual inspection of medical image samples compressed using EICA based selected ICs and adaptive ZQCP predictor model

WLANS SIMULATION TRANSCIEVER BASED DCT COMPRESSION

BER versus E_s/N_0 and PSNR versus BER for the IEEE 802.11b DBPSK modulation technique over AWGN was examined with $E_s/N_0 > 10$ to reduce BER in medical data using DCT compression during WLAN transceiver simulation. Therefore, simulation of WLAN transmission protocol was examined for fundus, X-ray, and cardiac data selected from the database. Six values of E_s/N_0 (i.e., 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, and 20 dB) were implemented to investigate effects of WLAN transmission protocol on BER and PSNR statistical measurements during transceiver simulation using DCT compression. Figure 8 displays achieved results of simulation of BER versus E_s/N_0 for the IEEE 802.11b DBPSK modulation over AWGN[11].

Figure 8: Mean PSNR and mean BER versus E_s/N_0 simulation results during transceiver of medical data with DCT compression for 802.11b DBPSK over AWGN channel, data Rate=1Mbps

Concepts of high PSNR and low BER measures were optimized to ensure good visual performance with less BERs using DCT medical data compression with different E_s/N_0 values[12]. Figure 8 shows polygraphs of PSNR and BER versus $E_s/N_0 = 10, 12, 14, 16, 18,$ and 20 . Using DBPSK, DCT compressed medical data during transceiver simulation can be tolerated at $E_s/N_0 \geq 14$ dB. Based on PSNR versus E_s/N_0 measurement results achieved, compressed medical data with high E_s/N_0 values during transceiver simulation yielded good visual performance with BER noise reduction compared with different E_s/N_0 values (i.e., 10, 12, and 14). High E_s/N_0 values resulted in high-quality data. Statistical measurement results are summarized in Table 3, which also shows high PSNR and low BER obtained after quantitative measurement of $E_s/N_0 \geq 14$.

TABLE 3: MEAN MEASURED VALUES OF BER AND PSNR VERSUS ES/NO DURING WLAN TRANSCIEVER SIMULATION BASED ON DCT COMPRESSED MEDICAL DATA

Image Type & Es/No	Fundus Images (Data Rate=1Mbps) (Blocking Size =8 by 8) (Coefficient kept=15%)		X-ray Images (Data Rate=1Mbps) (Blocking Size =8 by 8) (Coefficient kept=18%)		Cardiac Ultrasound Images (Data Rate=1Mbps) (Blocking Size =8 by 8) (Coefficient kept=22%)		
	Es/No	BER	PSNR	BER	PSNR	BER	PSNR
10 dB		0.0014646	16.397	0.0014371	16.6887	0.0014707	15.0839
12 dB		5.3310e-06	27.5964	7.4617e-05	31.0196	7.3039e-05	24.4121
14 dB		8.7918e-06	33.6482	1.2173e-05	38.3773	1.1271e-05	26.0369
16 dB		8.1155e-06	33.6482	1.1497e-05	41.1051	1.0370e-05	26.0369
18 dB		8.1155e-06	33.6482	1.1722e-05	37.9544	1.0595e-05	26.0369
20 dB		8.1155e-06	33.6482	1.1497e-05	41.1051	1.0595e-05	26.0369

VISUAL INSPECTION OF WLANS TRANSCIEVER BASED DCT

Figures 9, 10, and 11 illustrate visual inspections of fundus, X-ray, and cardiac data test samples, respectively, using WLAN transceiver simulation based on DCT compression and their corresponding resulting images with noise levels of 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, and 20 dB examined after analyzing noise effects on WLAN protocol during transceiver simulation[13].

Figure 9: Visual inspection of WLANs transceiver simulation based DCT compression (a) original fundus image and resulting compressed images via selected Es/No values (b) 10 dB, (c) 12 dB, (d) 14 dB (e) 16 dB (f) 18 dB and (g) 20 dB

Figure 10: Visual inspection of WLANs transceiver simulation based DCT compression (a) original X-ray image and resulting compressed images via selected Es/No values (b) 10 dB, (c) 12 dB, (d) 14 dB (e) 16 dB (f) 18 dB and (g) 20 dB

Figure 11: Visual inspection of WLANs transceiver simulation based DCT compression (a) original cardiac ultrasound image and resulting compressed images via selected Es/No values (b) 10 dB, (c) 12 dB, (d) 14 dB (e) 16 dB (f) 18 dB and (g) 20 dB

WLAN TRANSCIVER SIMULATION BASED ON EICA

The concept of high PSNR and low BER measures was optimized to ensure good visual performance with less BERs in terms of WLAN transceiver simulation based on EICA compression with different Es/No values. BER versus Es/No and PSNR versus BER for the IEEE 802.11b DBPSK modulation technique over AWGN were also examined with selected Es/No values to decrease BER and increase PSNR performance[14]. Therefore, simulation of WLAN transmission was examined using identical medical data selected from the database. Six values of Es/No=10, 12, 14,16,18, 20dB were implemented to investigate effects ofWLAN transmission on PSNR and BER statistical measures of EICA medical data compression during transceiver simulation. Figure 12 summarizes simulation results achieved for PSNR and BER versus Es/No of the IEEE 802.11b DBPSK modulation over AWGN.

Figure 12: Mean PSNR and mean BER versus Es/No simulation results during transceiver of medical data with EICA compression for 802.11b DBPKS over AWGN channel, data rate=1Mbps

Figure 12 illustrates plotty plots of PSNR and BER versus different Es/No values. Using DBPSK, EICA compressed medical data during transceiver simulation can be tolerated at Es/No ≥ 14 dB. Based on results achieved in PSNR versus Es/No measurement, compressed medical data with high Es/No values during transceiver simulation yielded good visual performance with BER noise reduction compared with different Es/No values (i.e., 10, 12, and 14). Statistical measurement results are summarized in Table 4, which also displays high PSNR and low BER obtained after quantitative measurement of Es/No ≥ 14 .

TABLE 4: MEASURED BER AND PSNR VERSUS ES/NO VALUES DURING WLAN TRANSCIVER SIMULATION BASED ON EICA COMPRESSED MEDICAL DATA

Image Type & Selected parameters	Fundus Images (Data Rate=1Mbps) (ZQCP predictor model) (ICs=8)		X-ray Images (Data Rate=1Mbps) (ZQCP predictor model) (ICs=8)		Cardiac Ultrasound Images (Data Rate=1Mbps) (ZQCP predictor model) (ICs=8)	
	Mean (BER)	Mean (PSNR)	Mean (MSE)	Mean (BER)	Mean (PSNR)	Mean (MSE)
Es/No						

10 dB	0.0014716	14.2142	0.014901	0.0014165	15.4039	0.01133
12 dB	5.7644e-05	26.0266	0.000981	6.4426e-05	29.0419	0.000490
14 dB	4.4771e-07	30.5120	0.000349	8.4771e-07	32.3540	0.000228
16 dB	4.2386e-07	30.5120	0.000349	4.2386e-07	32.3540	0.000228
18 dB	4.2386e-07	31.6415	0.000269	4.2386e-07	32.3540	0.000228
20 dB	4.2386e-07	31.6415	0.000269	4.2386e-07	32.4937	0.000221

VISUAL INSPECTION OF WLAN TRANSCIEVER SIMULATION BASED ON EICA

Figures 13, 14, and 15 illustrate visual inspections of fundus, X-ray, and cardiac data test samples using WLAN transceiver simulation based on EICA compression and their corresponding resulting images with noise levels of 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, and 20 dB after analyzing noise effects on WLAN protocol during transceiver simulation[2].

Figure 13: Visual inspection of WLANs transceiver simulation based on EICA compression of (a) original fundus image and resulting compressed images via selected Es/No values (b) 10 dB, (c) 12 dB, (d) 14 dB (e) 16 dB (f) 18 dB and (g) 20 dB

Figure 14: Visual inspection of WLANs transceiver simulation based on EICA compression of (a) original X-ray image and resulting compressed images via selected Es/No values (b) 10 dB, (c) 12 dB, (d) 14 dB (e) 16 dB (f) 18 dB and (g) 20 dB

Figure 15 Visual inspection of WLANs transceiver simulation based on EICA compression of (a) original cardiac ultrasound image and resulting compressed images via selected Es/No values (b) 10 dB, (c) 12 dB, (d) 14 dB (e) 16 dB (f) 18 dB and (g) 20 dB

WLAN TRANSCEIVER SIMULATION BASED ON COMPRESSION APPROACH SUMMARY

This section discusses evaluation performance of compression algorithms during WLAN transceiver simulation, used BER to quantify a channel carrying data by counting the rate of errors in a data string. Three types of medical data were compressed using different algorithms (i.e., DCT, SPIHT, JPEG2000, and EICA). The entire dataset has been employed to produce comparison analysis includes 100 of each x-ray images, 100 of fundus images and 100 of cardiac ultrasound images. Results of WLAN transceiver simulation of compressed data were evaluated in terms of BER and PSNR, respectively by employing the proposed EICA with the different compression DCT algorithms[3].

The results of the proposed EICA compression algorithm using all medical data yielded a higher PSNR score compared with other compression algorithm using DCT respectively. These measurement results are indicated in Table 5, where the PSNR quantitative measurement of EICA is shown to have mean PSNR of (33.6152) followed by DCT (32.8719), respectively, which is found EICA to have the highest PSNR in entire medical datasets.

By contrast, in determining BER amount based on all medical data, mean BER scores obtained using the EICA algorithm were significantly lower than those obtained using DCT algorithms. In general, a significant improvement in mean BER was observed, with a mean score of $0.0019e-04$ when using EICA compression algorithm compared with mean scores of 1.2986, using DCT algorithms, respectively. Such results presented smaller mean BER scores obtained using the WLAN-based EICA algorithm than those obtained using WLAN-based DCT algorithms for all medical data. By contrast, mean PSNR scores obtained using WLAN transceiver simulation based on DCT compression algorithms were superior to those obtained using WLAN transceiver simulation based on the EICA algorithm and in turn yielded good visual performance using all data.

1. In terms of BER of WLAN transceiver simulation, a significant improvement was observed in mean BERs score obtained using EICA compression algorithm compared with this obtained using DCT compression algorithms.
2. Significant effects were observed in PSNR scores obtained using WLAN transceiver simulation based on DCT compression algorithms compared with this obtained using WLAN

transceiver simulation based on the EICA algorithm. In conclusion, BER and PSNR scores obtained using WLAN transceiver simulation based on EICA compression algorithm with different medical data can compress medical data with low BER and good visual performance rate compared to the other algorithms. Comparative score results summarized in Table 5 indicate that WLAN transceiver simulation based on compression algorithms affected BER and PSNR performances.

TABLE 5: COMPARATIVE STATISTICAL MEASUREMENT OBTAINED USING WLAN TRANSCIEVER SIMULATION BASED ON DCT AND EICA COMPRESSION ALGORITHMS

Image type Algorithms	Fundus Images		X-ray Images		CardiacUltrasound Images		Mean (PSNR)
	Mean (BER)	Mean (PSNR)	Mean (BER)	Mean (PSNR)	Mean (BER)	Mean (PSNR)	
DCT+ WLANs	0.0867e-04	34.1002	0.1075e-04	38.4604	0.1025e-04	26.0550	32.8719
EICA+ WLANs	0.0019e-04	33.4790	0.0015e-04	38.5397	0.0015e-04	28.8267	33.6152

CONCLUSION

This research presents the development of Medata-SIM system for medical data WLAN transceiver simulation to aid in diagnosis assessment. In healthcare and hospital networks, medical data transceiver over WLAN presents an issue because of the growing size of medical data. Therefore, medical data compression plays a vital role in decreasing communication bandwidth and saving transmitting power. A prototype system was developed and implemented for medical data compression and transceiver over WLAN. This study showed feasibility and capability of using medical data compression and WLAN transceiver knowledge in assisting medical practitioners in conducting visualization and rapid diagnoses assessments.

The database used in this research consisted of fundus images, digital X-ray images, and ultrasound cardiac frames. These data were collected from different sources. As indicated previously, X-ray images were collected from NHANES II, which is maintained by the Lister Hill National Center Biomedical Communications in NLM at the NIH. Fundus images and ultrasound cardiac video were collected from available public online databases. The different medical data compression algorithms examined includes DCT, EICA, were used to describe and identify the amount of data compressed and visual appearance quality.

In this research, the results of different compression techniques are compared i.e. Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT), and the proposed Enhanced independent component Analysis (EICA). The effects of the different number of decompositions, image contents, and compression ratios are examined. The results of the above techniques are compared by using different parameters such as Compression Ratio, PSNR and MSE values from the reconstructed image. Findings are as follows:

CONCLUSION BASED COMPRESSION APPROACHES

Most image compression techniques achieve good data compression ratio. The tradeoff between data compression remains one of the difficult problems. Maintaining high compression with a good image is possible at a more or less high computational cost. One of the main goals for image compression is the reduce redundancy in the image block as much as possible. That is, it is very important to represent an image with a few bits as possible while maintaining good image quality. The results of the above techniques are compared and analyzed and the findings are as follow:

1. With regard to the DCT compression, the algorithm showed promising results in the three different medical data compressions, with an overall compression ratio of mean CR = 1.2986 and overall quality images of PSNR = 34.3636 in all medical data.

2. With regard to EICA compression, the algorithm showed talented results in the three different medical data compressions, all data improved, and compression results with the EICA showed satisfactory performance, with an overall CR = 3.567 and PSNR = 33.788. The EICA algorithm is coupled with adaptive ZQCP prediction model and yields significant compression with little quality loss.

Overall, when comparing the EICA compression with other compression algorithms, such DCT, it can be concluded that medical images compression via EICA outperforms image compression using other algorithms for the entire image tested with good appearance performance using all algorithms.

COMPRESSION AND WLANS APPROACHES

In the compression and WLANs transceiver, all the compressed medical data during WLAN transceiver simulation were validated using BER and PSNR statistical measurements to examine BER and the visual appearance performance via compression algorithms. The results of the above techniques with WLANs transceiver are compared, analyzed and the findings are as follow:

1. With regard to WLAN transceiver simulation based on DCT compression, the algorithm showed promising results on different medical data during WLAN transceiver simulation, with overall BER = 9.889e-06 and mean accuracy score of PSNR = 32.8719.

2. WLAN transceiver based on EICA compression, the performance of proposed compression algorithms was evaluated by the test images. EICA compression during WLAN transceiver simulation exhibited excellent results on all tested data with an overall BER = 1.6539e-07 and PSNR accuracy score = 33.6152 during WLAN transmission.

Generally, when comparing the WLANs with EICA compression with other compression algorithms, such DCT it can be concluded that medical images compression via EICA and WLANs transmission outperforms great visual performances using other algorithms for the entire image tested.

1. When evaluating WLANs with EICA compression, it is concluded that in general EICA has lower BER score obtained compare to WLAN transceiver based on DCT algorithms using all medical data. Thus, the overall PSNR scores obtained using WLAN transceiver based on EICA was superior to those obtained using WLAN transceiver based DCT algorithms. EICA perform well in the WLANs transmission approach and provides good visual performance rates.

2. When comparing the WLANs with EICA compression with other compression algorithms, such DCT in term of computational cost, it can be concluded that EICA and WLANs transmission outperforms acceptable processing times and EICA can fulfill application requirements in terms of WLAN transceiver simulation of medical data compression with less error and computation cost with great compression ratio and visual performance rates.

3. In addition, the main research objective was achieved by development of three main modules, namely, CS, TRS, and OTS. For data compression with suitable and effective performance, CS involved three different approaches in compressing medical data DCT and EICA algorithms. TRS was processed using WLAN with low bandwidth transmission. Finally, OTS was used for decompression and visualization of resulting data. Consequently, all three modules (i.e., CS, TRS, and OTS) were integrated to develop a computerized system called Medata-SIM.

In terms of system design, the developed system demonstrated promising results in compressing transceiver medical data. In conclusion, this research achieved the stated goal of developing a Medata-SIM computerized system, which affords medical data compression and WLAN

transceiver simulation for visualization and diagnosis assessment to aid medical practitioners in conducting rapid diagnoses.

RESEARCH CONTRIBUTION

The major contributions of the research toward accomplishing objectives and steps specified previously are briefly described as follows:

1. A new proposed compression algorithm named EICA based zero quantification coefficient percentage (ZQCP) model was successfully demonstrated for compression and WLANs transceiver simulation. Accordingly, EICA provides great compression ration with good image quality visualization for diagnostic assessment for medical practitioners in conducting rapid diagnoses.
2. A new reliable prototype system called Medata-SIM was developed for medical data compression and WLAN transceiver. This prototype system for compression and WLAN transceiver simulation operates on a collection of fundus, X-ray, and cardiac data. Prototype system simulation based compression algorithms by measuring CR, PSNR and visual appearance display. Functionality, performance results, and compression technical issues were also discussed. In summary, applications of EICA and Medata-SIM frameworks enable good compression and WLAN transceiver simulation for simulated medical data diagnosis. This computer-assisted system provides a valid, effective, robust, and reliable system applicable in the healthcare industry.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research was funded by the Ministry of Higher Education Libya and Elmergib University

REFERENCES

- [1] M. A. Algaet, Z. A. B. M. Noh, A. S. Shibghatullah, A. A. Milad, and A. Mustapha, "Provisioning quality of service of wireless telemedicine for e-health services: A review," *Wireless Personal Communications*, vol. 78, pp. 375-406, 2014.
- [2] M. A. Algaet, Z. A. M. Noh, A. Basari, A. Shibghatullah, A. Milad, and A. Mustapha, "A review of service quality in integrated networking system at the hospital scenarios," *Journal of Telecommunication, Electronic and Computer Engineering (JTEC)*, vol. 7, pp. 61-69, 2015.
- [3] M. A. Algaet, Z. A. B. M. Noh, A. S. Shibghatullah, and A. A. Milad, "Provisioning quality of service of wireless telemedicine for e-health services," in *2013 IEEE Conference on Information & Communication Technologies*, 2013, pp. 199-202.
- [4] A. Mustapha, A. Oulefki, M. Bengherabi, E. Boutellaa, and M. Almahdi Algaet, "Towards nonuniform illumination face enhancement via adaptive contrast stretching," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 76, pp. 21961-21999, 2017.
- [5] M. A. Algaet, Z. A. B. M. Noh, A. S. Shibghatullah, A. A. Milad, and A. Mustapha, "A review on provisioning quality of service of wireless telemedicine for E-health services," *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research*, vol. 19, pp. 570-592, 2014.
- [6] M. A. Algaet, Z. A. B. Muhamad Noh, A. S. Shibghatullah, A. A. Milad, and A. Mustapha, "Telemedicine and its application in healthcare management: Telemedicine management," ed: Outskirts Press, 2014.
- [7] T. K. Soon, N. K. Ibrahim, B. Hussin, A. Idris, N. M. Yaacob, M. A. Algaet, *et al.*, "The utilization of feature based Viola-Jones method for face detection in invariant rotation," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 9, 2018.
- [8] M. A. Algaet, Z. A. B. M. Noh, A. S. B. H. Basari, A. S. Shibghatullah, A. A. Milad, A. B. Abugharsa, *et al.*, "Development of robust medical image transmission via Wi-Fi IEEE 802.11 b in the hospital area," *Wireless Personal Communications*, vol. 95, pp. 1617-1634, 2017.
- [9] M. A. Algaet, Z. A. B. M. Noh, A. S. Shibghatullah, and A. A. Milad, "A review on framework and quality of service based web services discovery," *European journal of scientific research*, vol. 111, pp. 300-322, 2013.
- [10] T. Malaysia, "Medical data compression and transmission in noisy WLANS: a review," *International Journal of grid and distributed computing*, vol. 12, pp. 1-18, 2019.
- [11] M. A. Algaet, Z. Noh, A. Basari, A. S. Shibghatullah, A. Milad, and A. Mustapha, "Simulation of medical data compression and transmission through WLANs," *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, vol. 82, p. 237, 2015.
- [12] M. A. M. Taloo and M. A. Algaet, "Comparative study of discrete cosine transforms and set partitioning in hierarchical trees," 2019.
- [13] M. A. Algaet, A. A. Milad, and S. H. Almadhun, "Enhanced Independent Components Analysis (EICA)," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 975, p. 8887.
- [14] N. Napi, A. Zaidan, B. Zaidan, O. Albahri, M. Alsalem, and A. Albahri, "Medical emergency triage and patient prioritisation in a telemedicine environment: a systematic review," *Health and Technology*, vol. 9, pp. 679-700, 2019.